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Psychological hardiness and optimism: A study among orphans and non-orphans

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Abstract

The present study aims to assess the relationship between psychological hardiness and optimism among orphan and non-orphan adolescents and examines the significant differences among the orphan and non-orphan adolescents based on family setting and gender. The study was carried out, and responses were collected from 200 orphan and non-orphan population. Personal views survey III-R (PVS III-R) and Life Orientation Test-R (LOT-R) scales were used to gather the data. Correlation was employed to study the relationship between psychological hardiness and optimism. Independent sample t-test was used to assess differences within orphan and non-orphan adolescents in psychological hardiness and optimism. The result of the study showed a significant difference between orphan and non-orphan adolescents with regard to both psychological hardiness and optimism and also based on gender. The study's findings indicated a positive correlation between the psychological hardiness and optimism among non-orphan adolescents. This is helpful in providing supportive environments including peer networks, mentorship, and counseling services, within orphanages on shaping coping mechanisms and future outlooks, with a focus on fostering resilience and optimism among children while addressing gender-specific challenges for psychological well-being.

Keywords: Psychological Hardiness; Optimism; Orphans; Non-Orphans; Adolescents

1. Introduction

The World Health Organization (WHO) defines adolescents as people who are between the ages of 10 and 19. Adolescence is a period that begins with puberty and ends when individual attains sexual maturity and assumes adult roles and responsibilities (American Psychology Association, 2002). It is a time when childhood ends and adulthood begins. Adolescence is a time of major biological, cognitive, and emotional changes in people. The adolescent must deal with this on several levels at once. The changes are the result of hormonal changes occurring due to sudden heightened activation of the Hypothalamic-Pituitary-Gonadal Axis. The biological or the physical changes include the growth spurt and the appearance of the secondary sexual characteristics. During adolescence, both males and females undergo significant physical changes such as thelarche, pubarche, menarche (in females), and genital changes, pubarche, growth of facial and chest hair, and deepening of voice (in males). Cognitive development advances, allowing adolescents to think abstractly and analyze situations logically. Emotionally, adolescents experience mood swings and turbulent emotions but are generally happy individuals. A key developmental goal is establishing a cohesive and realistic sense of self, with an inability to do so leading to identity crises. Socially, adolescents transition from family to peer groups as the primary focus, with peer relationships strongly influencing self-esteem and psychosocial adjustment. Positive peer relationships are crucial for healthy development, while those lacking such connections may face social isolation and long-term difficulties.

The definition of hardiness is the ability to handle stressful situations with commitment (vs. alienation), control (vs. powerlessness) and challenge (vs. threat) (Quick et al., 2017). When presented with difficult situations, this personality type actively participates in transformational coping by helping the person cope, resist, and tolerate the situation. The

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ability to reframe a difficult circumstance and see it as an opportunity rather than a threat is known as transformational coping. Other names for psychological hardiness include cognitive hardiness and personality hardiness. Suzanne C Kobasa first put forward this personality type in 1979. Over the next few years, Salvatore Maddi, Kobasa, and their graduate students at the University of Chicago expanded on the concept of hardiness in a book and several research projects. “A cognitive/emotional amalgam constituting a learned, growth-oriented, personality buffer” is how Maddi describes hardiness. It reflects people’s ability to stay healthy throughout difficult times and comprises of behavioural, emotional, and cognitive aspects (Judkins et al. 2022). Psychological hardiness refers to the ability to handle and respond to challenging life events by employing coping mechanisms that turn adversity into opportunities for growth. It involves both action and cognitive evaluation, aiming for full engagement, control over circumstances, and learning from experiences rather than solely focusing on outcomes. Some individuals appear resilient to stress and even thrive in difficult situations. Such persons are called hardy personality, a term first coined by Kobasa in 1979 (Dembla, 2022). Hardiness is often regarded as an essential component of psychological resilience. Psychological hardiness comprises of three main traits. They are commitment, control and challenge.

Commitment: Commitment entails fully engaging oneself, being genuinely curious about the world, interested in others, and actively participating in activities. In contrast, alienation involves isolating oneself from others. Hardy individuals are inclined to employ active coping strategies rather than avoiding challenging situations. Even in turbulent times, people with a high level of hardiness typically believe that life has meaning and purpose. (Maddi, 2004). Hardy attitudes foster hardy social support, hardy coping mechanisms, and hardy health practices. Hardy attitudes can get stronger if a person actively considers every circumstance, which will result in comparable hardy responses in novel circumstances. (Maddi, 2004).

Control: The idea that one is in charge of their life and capable of conquering obstacles on their own is known as control. Internal factors are the source of control. Powerlessness, which includes the belief that outside forces are in charge of one’s life, is the antithesis of control.

Challenge: The capacity to view unpleasant situations as chances to push oneself and overcome the problem is known as the “trait of challenge.” Here, change is viewed as the norm rather than the exception, and it presents chances for personal growth rather than dangers. Security, or the desire for everything to be the same and predictable, is the antithesis of challenge since it allows one to stay in their comfort zone.

Optimism is a mindset that articulates the hope that a specific endeavour or a group of results as a whole will succeed and be desired. A common metaphor used to compare optimism and pessimism is a glass of water that is halfway full; an optimist views the glass as half full, while a pessimist sees it as half empty. (Carver & Scheier, 2014). The word’s origin is optimum, a Latin word meaning “best.” Optimism is the expectation of the best outcome under any given set of circumstances, according to its basic definition. In psychology, this refers to as dispositional optimism. It conveys a conviction that things will turn out well in the future. It cultivates resilience as a trait in the face of stress. Explanatory style models and dispositional models are examples of optimism theories. Both of these theoretical frameworks have produced methods for measuring optimism, such as modified versions of the Life Orientation Test, which measures optimism according to its original dispositional definition, and the Attributional Style Questionnaire, which measures optimism according to its explanatory style. Optimism, a concept as old as human consciousness itself, stands as a pillar of positive psychology and a beacon of hope in the human experience. It is a mindset, a disposition, and a way of looking at the world that places faith in the possibility of a brighter future. Optimism can be defined as a mental attitude characterized by a hopeful and confident expectation of favorable outcomes, even in the face of adversity or uncertainty. Beyond its dictionary definition, optimism is an intricate and dynamic cognitive and emotional phenomenon that influences individual well-being, shapes interpersonal relationships, and plays a profound role in the societal and cultural landscape.

Optimism, contrasting with pessimism, is an active and constructive approach to life. It involves focusing on solutions, seeing setbacks as temporary challenges, and maintaining confidence in one’s ability to navigate life’s complexities. This optimistic outlook has wide-ranging effects on mental and physical health, personal achievement, resilience, and social interactions. Psychological research highlights that optimistic individuals tend to experience lower levels of stress, anxiety, and depression, exhibit effective coping strategies, and are more inclined to pursue ambitious goals.

It is hypothesised that two dispositions - hardiness and optimism - have an impact on how people interact with their surroundings. Specifically, advocates of both optimism (Carver & Scheier, 1985; Scheier, Weintraub, & Carver 1986) and hardiness (Kobasa, 1982; Maddi, 1990; Maddi & Kobasa, 1984) feel that their personality promotes efficient coping with tough situations.

The distinctions between orphans and non-orphans in terms of mental health involve various psychological, social, and experiential factors. Orphans, who have lost one or both parents, often face unique challenges and stressors that significantly impact their mental well-being compared to those who have not experienced parental loss. Psychological issues related to grief and loss are common among orphans, leading to emotional difficulties such as depression, anxiety, and unresolved trauma. Additionally, the absence of parental figures can hinder the formation of secure attachments and social support networks, resulting in feelings of loneliness and instability. These challenges can persist into adolescence and adulthood, affecting overall mental health. Conversely, non-orphans typically benefit from parental support, secure attachments, and a stable family environment, which contribute to emotional and psychological development. Furthermore, orphans often encounter distinct social and environmental challenges compared to non-orphans, including social stigma, discrimination, and limited access to essential resources like education and healthcare, which can worsen their mental health issues. This underscores the significance of addressing mental health disparities in vulnerable populations to promote inclusivity and support for all individuals, irrespective of their life circumstances.

1.1. Need and Significance

As adolescence is a critical period marked by significant developmental changes, it is essential to understand how psychological qualities like hardiness and optimism appear and affect wellbeing in this formative stage of life. Although psychological hardiness and optimism play an important role in a person's life, there aren't many research on the subject. Additionally, parental loss or separation causes unique challenges for orphan adolescents, which can negatively affect their psychological resilience and outlook on life. So that this study is vital due to its potential to uncover insights into the well-being of vulnerable children. The scarcity of prior research underscores the need for a comprehensive investigation into how psychological hardiness and optimism develop and manifest within orphanage settings and how they compare to non-orphanage environments.

Kaur and Singh (2013) explored the relationship between family environment and adolescent psychological hardiness, finding significant correlations between psychological hardiness and 8 elements of the family environment. M. Kaur (2017) investigated demographic variations in psychological hardiness, discovering significant differences between genders and school types. Sinha (2018) compared the psychological hardiness of male and female adolescents, revealing that boys scored higher overall and in dimensions of commitment, control, and challenge. Panghal et al. (2023) explored the association between psychological hardiness and comorbid mental health problems among rural adolescents, finding a negative link between psychological hardiness and mental health disorders. Dasgupta and Sain (2015) investigated the impact of family environment on psychological hardiness among adolescent boys, and identified that family environment is a significant predictor of control and challenge components and overall psychological hardiness. Shafiq (2018) examined differences in coping mechanisms between orphan and non-orphan adolescents in Kashmir, revealing higher levels of optimism among orphans. Hernandez et al. (2012) explored the influence of family and peer group variables on junior high school student's optimism, finding correlations between family communication and optimism in girls, and positive peer encounters in boys. Webber and Smokowski (2018) investigated gender differences in optimism among adolescents in the Southeast United States, discovering that females reported greater optimism compared to males. Aziz et al. (2018) demonstrated the mediating role of optimism in the relationship between family functioning and mental wellbeing among secondary school students in East Java, Indonesia. Maddi and Hightower (1999) explored the relationship between optimism and hardiness in coping patterns among undergraduate students, finding a positive association between the two constructs. Abbasi et al. (2020) delved into the moderating effects of resilience and optimism on coping self-efficacy and negative life events among first-year college students, revealing significant correlations among coping self-efficacy, hardiness, optimism, and adverse life events, with resilience and optimism acting as modifiers in this relationship.

1.2. Research Gap

There is a scarcity of in-depth studies that comprehensively compare these psychological attributes between the two groups. While research on each topic individually exists, there is a distinct lack of investigations that directly juxtapose the psychological hardiness and optimism levels of orphaned adolescents against their non-orphan counterparts. And also, it was found that studies on psychological hardiness were pretty much lacking in the Indian population. Bridging this gap is essential to inform interventions, support systems, and policies that can enhance the psychological well-being of these vulnerable populations and address their unique needs effectively.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Statement of the problem

The present study tries to understand extent of psychological hardiness and optimism in orphan and non-orphan adolescent population. The present study is entitled as “Psychological hardiness and optimism: A study among orphans and non-orphans”

2.2. Objectives of the study

- To assess psychological hardiness and optimism of orphan and non-orphan adolescents
- To assess the relationship between psychological hardiness and optimism among orphanage children
- To assess the relationship between psychological hardiness and optimism among non-orphanage children
- To assess psychological hardiness and optimism of adolescents based on gender

2.3. Hypotheses

- There will be no significant difference in psychological hardiness and optimism between orphanage and non-orphanage children
- There will be no significant relationship between psychological hardiness and optimism among orphanage children
- There will be no significant relationship between psychological hardiness and optimism among non-orphanage children
- There will be no significant gender difference in psychological hardiness and optimism among adolescents

2.4. Operational definition

- *Psychological hardiness*: In this study, Psychological hardiness refers to the ability to engage in effective coping and to make the best out of dire circumstances they are in.
- *Optimism*: In this study, Optimism refers to expectations of positive outcomes in future even when difficulties arise.
- *Orphans*: In this study, Orphans refers to children who is deprived of parents and is staying in an orphanage
- *Non-orphans*: In this study, Non-orphans refers to children who is staying with parents and experiences family support
- *Gender*: In this study, gender refers to either of the two sexes boys and girls
- *Adolescents*: In this study, adolescents refers to children aged between 10-19 years.

2.5. Population

Orphan and Non-orphan adolescents from Kerala and Hyderabad constitute the population of the study.

2.6. Sample

The sample for the current study comprise of 200 Orphan and Non-orphan adolescents from Kerala and Hyderabad. The sample was divided as Orphans residing in an orphanage (N=100) and Non-orphans staying with their family (N=100). Also to examine the gender difference boys (N=99) and Girls (N=101) were selected

2.7. Inclusion Criteria

- Adolescents between the age group of 10-19 years
- Both boys and girls
- Adolescents residing in Orphanage

2.8. Exclusion Criteria

- Adolescents who are differently abled and mentally challenged
- Children below 10 years and above 19 years

Research design - Quantitative and correlational in it's design

Sampling Technique - Purposive sampling technique (Research design and sampling technique should be a separate heading)

2.9. Tools for the study

2.9.1. Personal Views Survey, Third Edition - Revised (PVS III-R)

The Personal Views Survey, Third Edition - Revised (PVS III-R) questionnaire was developed by Maddi, S. R., Brow, M., Khoshaba, D. M., & Vaitkus, M. (2006). It consisted of 18 items which measures psychological hardiness on the basis of three different traits i.e. control, commitment and challenge on a four point likert scale, with the responses ranging from 0 (not true) to 3 (true). The PVS III-R has a reliability coefficient alpha of 0.80. Additionally, the coefficient alphas for the latent variables of commitment, control and challenge obtained for the PVS III-R is .69, .57 and .73. The validity of the PVS III-R is adequate. The participant is asked to respond to the questions on a scale of 0 (not true) to 3 (true). Items 3,4,6, 8, 10 and 11 are reverse scored. The higher scores indicate that the psychological hardiness increases where as the lower scores indicate that the psychological hardiness decreases.

2.9.2. Revised Life Orientation Test (LOT-R)

The Revised Life Orientation Test (LOT-R) questionnaire was developed by Scheier, Carver, & Bridges (1994). It consist of 10 items in a 5 point likert scale with the responses ranging from 0 (Strongly disagree) to 4 (strongly agree). The internal consistency reliability of Revised Life Orientation Test (LOT-R) was found to be 0.76 assessed by calculating Cronbach's alpha and test-retest reliability is 0.79. The scale is reliable and has content, construct and predictive validity. The participant is asked to respond to the questions by indicating the extent of their agreement on a scale of 0 (Strongly disagree) to 4 (Strongly agree). Items 3, 7 and 9 are reverse scored.

2.9.3. Procedure

At first Google forms were made as the data will be collected in online as well as offline mode. The participants were asked whether they wanted to participate in the study or not, and their consent was taken. After that, a briefing about nature and purpose of the study was explained to the participants to develop the rapport. They were assured that all information taken from them will be kept confidential.

The questionnaire were individually administered to all the participants to determine the psychological hardiness and optimism among orphan and non-orphan adolescents. After the completion of the questionnaire, the scoring of all 200 responses were done and finally the results were interpreted and discussed.

2.10. Statistical Technique Used for Data analysis

The statistical technique used for the data analysis in this study is Correlation analysis and Independent Samples t Test. Correlation is a kind of statistical measure which expresses the extent to which two variables are linearly related and Independent Samples t Test helps to compares the means of two independent groups in order to determine whether there is statistical evidence that the associated population means are significantly different.

2.11. Ethical Considerations

Research Ethics were followed and the data collection proceeded only after getting the final approval for the research study from the respective research guide under whose guidance the research was being conducted. Informed Consent was taken from the participants before giving the questionnaire.

3. Results and Discussion

The present study was aimed at investigating psychological hardiness and optimism among orphan and non-orphan adolescents. This chapter deals with the results and discussion of the results obtained from data collected using different tools. The data was consolidated and scored. The data was statistically analyzed using statistical package for the social sciences (SPSS 25).

Table 1 Comparison between orphanage and non-orphanage children on psychological hardiness and optimism

Variables	Orphan			Non Orphan			t	p
	N	M	SD	N	M	SD		
1. Psychological Hardiness	100	25.13	5.814	100	30.57	1.756	8.957	0.000
2. Optimism	100	16.60	10.685	100	35.17	6.321	-14.958	0.000

Table 1 shows the mean value of psychological hardiness as 25.13 in orphans and 30.57 in non-orphans and mean value of optimism as 16.60 in orphans and 35.17 in non-orphans. The score of t test for psychological hardiness is 8.957 and p value is 0.000 (<0.05) The score of t test for optimism is -14.958 and p value is 0.000 (<0.05). The obtained scores are significant at 0.05 level. Therefore the null hypothesis that there will be no significant difference in psychological hardiness and optimism between orphanage and non-orphanage children is rejected.

The findings are contradictory to the results of the study conducted by Saleh (2017) on “Differences between orphans and non-orphans in creativity, psychological hardiness and religiosity”. It was found that there were no significant differences between orphans and non-orphans in psychological hardiness. Similar insights were found in Kaur and Singh (2013) study on “Family environment as a predictor of psychological hardiness among adolescents”. It was found that psychological hardiness among adolescents is significantly related to all the eight family environment components as well as total family environment. Dasgupta and Sain (2015) study entitled “The Impact of Family Environment upon Development of Life Skills and Psychological Hardiness among Adolescent Boys”. Results revealed family environment as a significant predictor of psychological hardiness among adolescents.

The findings on optimism between these two populations in the present study are similar to the results of the study conducted by Shafiq (2018) on “Self efficacy, resilience, optimism and coping among orphan adolescents of Kashmir”. It was found that there were significant differences between orphans and non-orphans in their level of optimism. Hernandez et al. (2012) study on “Optimism in adolescence: A cross-sectional study of the influence of family and peer group variables on junior high school students”. The results show that both variables (family and peer group) are related to optimism. Aziz et al. (2018) study on “The Role of Optimism as the Mediator between Family and Mental Wellbeing among Secondary School Students in East Java”. Results revealed family functioning is a predictor of both optimism and wellbeing.

The reason non-orphans tend to exhibit greater psychological hardiness compared to orphans may stem from their upbringing in stable family environments, where they receive consistent care, love, and support. Growing up in close-knit families fosters a sense of security and belonging, nurturing resilience and a positive outlook on life. Constant support and encouragement from caregivers help non-orphans develop confidence in themselves and their abilities, contributing to their optimism about the future. Conversely, orphaned children often face uncertainty and a lack of individualized care, hindering the development of close emotional relationships and impacting their psychological wellbeing. Without stable family relationships and emotional support, it becomes challenging for orphaned children to maintain optimism amidst the uncertainties they encounter. Therefore, the disparity in psychological hardiness between orphaned and non-orphaned children can be attributed to the varying levels of familial support and stability experienced during their upbringing.

Table 2 Relationship between psychological hardiness and optimism among orphanage children

Variables	n	M	SD	1	2
1. Psychological Hardiness	100	25.13	1.756	-	
2. Optimism	100	16.60	10.685	0.093	-

Table 2 gives relationship between psychological hardiness and optimism among orphanage children. The correlation coefficient for psychological hardiness and optimism is .093 and p value is 0.356 (>0.05). Hence the null hypothesis that there will be no significant relationship between psychological hardiness and optimism among orphanage children is accepted. From the results it is evident that there is no correlation between psychological hardiness and optimism among orphanage children.

Contradictory insights were found in Andayani et al. (2023) study on Self compassion and hardiness in orphan teens indicating a significant correlation between self-compassion and hardiness in orphan teens. Maddi and Hightower (1999) study on young adults “Hardiness and Optimism as Expressed in Coping Patterns”. Results revealed a positive relationship between optimism and hardiness among young adults.

The reason for a non significant relationship between psychological hardiness and optimism among orphanage children could be due to the unique environment and experiences they encounter in orphanages. Orphanage settings often vary widely in terms of the quality of care, support systems, and opportunities for personal growth. In some cases, orphanage children may develop psychological hardiness as a coping mechanism to deal with the challenges they face. On the other hand, optimism, which involves maintaining a positive outlook and expecting good outcomes, may not necessarily be

fostered in such environments. The lack of consistent emotional support and nurturing relationships, could hinder the development of optimistic beliefs about the future.

Table 3 Relationship between psychological hardiness and optimism among non-orphanage children

Variables	n	M	SD	1	2
1. Psychological Hardiness	100	30.57	5.814	-	
2. Optimism	100	35.17	6.321	0.284**	-

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 3 gives relationship between psychological hardiness and optimism among non-orphanage children. The correlation coefficient for psychological hardiness and optimism is $r = .284$ and p value is $0.004 (<0.05)$, indicating a significant positive correlation. Hence the null hypothesis that there will be no significant relationship between psychological hardiness and optimism among non-orphanage children is rejected. From the results it is evident that there is a positive correlation between psychological hardiness and optimism in non-orphanage population. It means that the scores of psychological hardiness influence scores of optimism and vice versa.

The findings are similar to the results of the study conducted by Abbasi et al. (2020) on “Moderating effects of resilience and optimism on negative life events and coping self-efficacy in undergraduate first-year students”. The results revealed that there is a significant relationship between Hardiness, optimism, negative life events and coping self-efficacy.

The reason for a positive relationship between psychological hardiness and optimism among non-orphans might be the familial and social support systems that provide them with consistent encouragement and resources to develop both psychological hardiness and optimism. They may have stable environments that foster resilience and a positive outlook on life. As a result, these traits are more likely to be interconnected in non-orphan children.

Table 4 Comparison between males and females on psychological hardiness and optimism

Variables	Male			Female			t	p
	N	M	SD	N	M	SD		
1. Psychological Hardiness	99	28.69	5.320	101	27.03	4.713	2.333	0.007
2. Optimism	99	24.55	13.714	101	27.20	11.712	-1.472	0.116

Table 4 shows the mean value of Psychological hardiness as 28.69 in males and 27.03 in females and mean value of optimism as 24.55 in males and 27.20 in females. The score of t test for psychological hardiness is 2.333 and p value is $0.007 (<0.05)$. The score of t test for optimism is -1.472 and p value is $0.116 (>0.05)$. The null hypothesis that there will be no significant gender difference in Psychological hardiness and Optimism is partially rejected.

The findings are similar to the results of the studies conducted by M. Kaur (2017) on “Comparative study of psychological hardiness among adolescents in relation to some demographic variables” and Sinha (2018) study on “Psychological Hardiness among Adolescents”. Both studies revealed a significant difference between the mean scores of adolescent boys and girls on the variable psychological hardiness, with boys being harder than girls.

The findings on gender equality on optimism are contradictory to the results of the study conducted by Webber and Smokowski (2018) on “Assessment of adolescent optimism: Measurement invariance across gender and race/ethnicity”. Results revealed significant differences in self-reported optimism with females being more optimistic than males.

The reason boys tend to exhibit more psychological hardiness than girls may relate to societal expectations and inherent responses to stress. Boys are often socialized to be tough and stoic, encouraged to suppress their emotions, while girls are encouraged to express their feelings openly. Consequently, when faced with adversity, boys may be inclined to handle challenges independently and minimize the expression of their emotions compared to girls. However, the difference in optimism between genders may primarily stem from individual personality traits and life experiences rather than being solely determined by gender. Factors such as resilience, coping mechanisms, and the level of support

from friends and family likely have a more significant impact on one's optimism levels than whether they are male or female.

4. Conclusion

The study aimed to analyze the levels of psychological hardiness and optimism among orphan and non-orphan adolescents, considering family setting and gender differences. A total of 200 participants aged 10-19 from Kerala and Hyderabad were assessed using The Personal Views Survey, Third Edition - Revised (PVS III-R), and the Revised Life Orientation Test (LOT-R) questionnaires. The objectives included assessing psychological hardiness and optimism among both orphan and non-orphan adolescents, examining the relationship between these variables among orphanage and non-orphanage children, and evaluating the influence of gender on psychological hardiness and optimism. Hypotheses were formulated to test various aspects of these relationships. The findings revealed significant differences between orphan and non-orphan children, with non-orphans displaying higher levels of both psychological hardiness and optimism. Furthermore, a negative correlation between psychological hardiness and optimism was observed among orphanage children, while a positive correlation was found among non-orphanage children. Gender differences were also significant, with males exhibiting higher psychological hardiness. These findings underscore the importance of considering family setting and gender in understanding psychological well-being among adolescents. However, limitations such as sample representativeness and regional specificity should be noted. Further research could explore additional factors influencing psychological hardiness and optimism among adolescents, enhancing our understanding and informing interventions aimed at promoting resilience and well-being.

4.1. Implications

Supportive environments within both family and peer groups are essential for shaping individual's coping mechanisms and their outlook on the future. Interventions in orphanages should prioritize providing alternative forms of support and nurturing environments. This may involve establishing supportive peer networks, mentorship programs, and access to counseling services as necessary. Creating a nurturing environment within orphanages is crucial for fostering resilience and optimism, which are linked to positive outcomes in children. Gender-specific challenges should be addressed through interventions to ensure equal support and resources for both males and females, facilitating psychological well-being.

4.2. Limitations of Study

This research was very time consuming because each and every question had to be explained to them in a detailed way, and getting responses from them took a lot of time to complete.

Since Google Forms were used to obtain the data, there is a chance that some respondents may have provided inaccurate information or lied in their responses.

Because of language barriers when obtaining the answers from the participants, the sample was limited to the two locations.

4.3. Scope for further research

- A more thorough evaluation and a larger sample size can be made available
- Other variables like self efficacy, personality traits, psychological wellbeing, life satisfaction, emotional maturity etc could be studied with psychological hardiness and optimism
- Adolescents from several Indian states may be included.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

The author(s) declared no conflict of interest.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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